

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND EFFECTIVENESS OF FOOD MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of food manufacturing firms in Nigeria is yet to be achieved, hence this study ascertained the extent to which selected human resource management practices influence the effectiveness of food manufacturing firms. Selected human resource management practices in the study are: learning and development, performance appraisal, reward management and employee relations. Primary data was sourced from employees of two food manufacturing firms situated in Lagos and Ogun state, Nigeria through the use of a closed ended structured questionnaire. Data retrieved were analyzed using PLS-SEM. The finding of the study ascertained that employee relation and reward management had a positive significant effect, while learning and development and performance appraisal had no significant effect on organizational effectiveness. It was concluded that the complexity that emanates from managing employees cannot be overlooked, however, ensuring proper employee relations and reward is an important factor to achieve effectiveness within an organization.

Keywords: Human resource management practice, Learning and development, Performance appraisal, Reward management, Employee relation, Organizational effectiveness

1.0 Introduction

Effectiveness is one of the performance indicators used to analyze the interaction of an organization's outputs with the economic and social environment (John-Eke & Akintokunbo, 2020). This is in line with the view of Eydi (2015) who stated that effectiveness is attained when the goals of the organization are achieved through the transforming of input to output so as to respond to expected demands. Tooksoon (2011) posits that for an organization to be effective, the human factor within the organization needs to be examined, as they are the lifeline of an organization. Fadun (2017) further supported this view and that achieving effectiveness is based on the extent to which the right skills, knowledge and abilities needed to carry out expected duties are acquired and developed. Thus, how employees are managed within an organization becomes an important factor to be considered in achieving organizational effectiveness.

Managing human resource within an organization requires putting some human resource management practices in place (Armstrong, 2016). These practices differ from one organization to the other and are most times used as a strategy for the organization to gain a competitive advantage over the others. Delery and Doty (1996) cited in Tan and Nasurdin (2011) conceptualized human resource management practices as “a set of internally consistent policies designed and implemented to ensure that a firm’s human capital contributes to the achievement of its business objectives”. This is to say that human resource management practices are the product of an organization’s human resource management policies. Putting in place the right human resource management practices within an organization becomes important as it establishes the enhancement of employees’ human capital by acquiring relevant knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics (Noe, Clarke & Klein, 2014); analyzing the contribution of each employee to the organization (Armstrong (2009); allocating employees with benefits and commendations schemes (David, Rajput, Khan & Raghuwanshi, 2015); and also ensuring that there exists a good interaction between organizations and their employees (Armstrong, 2012). Thus, in this study, the human resource management practices concentrated on are employees’ learning and development, employees’ performance appraisal, employees’ reward management and employees’ relations.

Statement of Problem

Nigeria is a nation blessed with abundant natural resources which can be utilized as raw materials in manufacturing basic human needs, primary among which is food. Despite this, the nation is still encountering major challenges in the course of producing goods and services to satisfy basic human needs (Omoniyi, 2018).

The Nigeria manufacturing sector which can put the nation’s economy among the biggest economies in the world considering the available resources is still struggling with 11.5% contribution to the nations GDP (World Bank, 2020). This sector which have been reported to be the driver of developed economies seems to be ineffective in developing countries as obvious in the state of their economies (UNIDO, 2018). Nigeria is not an exemption from this as Abolo (2017) stated that improvement in the manufacturing sector is still stagnant. In Nigeria, despite the pronounced involvement in growing, processing and selling of food, immediate consumption needs are far from being met (Pfitzer and Krishnawamy, 2017), thereby leaving the food sub-sector of Nigeria manufacturing firm ineffective. This state of ineffectiveness becomes disturbing, especially when considering the resuscitation made by the Nigerian governments to the manufacturing sector.

Specifically, in the food sector between 2015 and now, ten manufacturing firms have reportedly shut down their operations due to a harsh working environment. Also, about twenty-four (24) firms within the same sector have massively retrenched their staff (Tribune Newspaper, May 30, 2021). Thus, the effectiveness of many food manufacturing firms in Nigeria is yet to be fully achieved. This corroborates the position of Afolabi and Laseinde (2019) that there has been a sluggish improvement in the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors and has made the sector ineffective.

Global Report on Food Crises (GRFC, 2021), noted that Nigeria is experiencing a serious deterioration in the food supply, thus, making the nation one of the six countries in Africa with a worsening food crisis. This has increased food prices and caused dissatisfaction on the part of the consumers (Trade Economic Report, 2021). The need to increase production by these food manufacturing firms raised alarm for effective and efficient utilization of both human and non-human resources, however, in the process of ensuring effective and efficient utilization of resources within the organization. Beheshtifar and Mahmoudi (2012) ascertained that there has been a tremendous issue of poor human resource management practices. This ranges from issues of labour casualization, massive retrenchment of workers, overloading employees with work (Adisa, Osabutey, Gbadamosi & Mordi, 2017), employees not being able to access global technical development (Jovanovis, Damnjanovic, Dimitrijevic, 2016), poor safety measures, inappropriate appraisal, and remuneration of employees, as well as poor channels of the relationship between employees and their employer (Tina & Wendy, 2017). This has therefore established the fact that human resource management practices have become more challenging, and no longer effective as they supposed to be.

Based on the premise above, this study intends to ascertain the extent to which the selected human resource management practices influence the effectiveness of food manufacturing firms.

2.0 Literature Review

Human resource management Practices

The managerial process through which the workforce of an organization are being accessed, rewarded, and the same time ensuring that the culture and leadership of the organization complies with employment and labour law was captured by Sunday and Nsobiari (2016) as Human resource management (HRM) practice. This activity includes identifying human resource needs, screening, hiring, training, rewarding, assessing employees, as well as dealing with employee relations, safety and health issues, and fairness problems (Dessler, 2007).

Human resource management practices are built on the human resource management's policies within the organization (Tan & Nasurdin, 2011). Mathis and John (2005) defined human resource management policies as rules and guidelines formally set by a business to hire, train, assess and reward employees working within the organization. They are procedures and values the organization anticipates to use in managing its people (Armstrong, 2016). This gives the basis and reference points of how manager deal with HR related matters. It is through these policies that human resource practitioners decide on the various human resource management practices to be adopted for their organization so that the organization can achieve its goals and objectives.

Armstrong (2010) believed that HR practices concentrates on the means an organization adopts in employing and managing people. This ranges from activities like resourcing (which requires planning, recruiting and selecting as well as managing talents), developing and managing human capital knowledge, managing performance, rewarding employees, while also ensuring

good relations and wellbeing of employees. To Hassan (2016), HR practices relating to training and development employees, appraising performance, planning employees' career, participation of employees and compensation are mostly relevant in an organization. Hence, four HR practices considered in this study are:

- i. Employee learning and development
- ii. Employee performance appraisal
- iii. Employee reward management
- iv. Employee relations

i. Employee Learning and Development

To keep and develop knowledgeable employees of high quality should be the main goal for every organization. This intensifies the need for organizations to desire and ensures that development of their employees is channeled through the proper direction, as employees need to be exposed to constant learning and development opportunities through proper evaluation, so as move forward on a routine basis (Vostrá, Jindrová & Dömeová, 2011). This practice gives room for employee's improvement, keeping and developing knowledgeable quality employees and at the same time creating a competitive advantage for the organization (Duggan & Media, 2013).

ii. Employee Performance Appraisal

With the advancements in industrial development, it is imperative to review the results of employee activities in order to boost efficiency while retaining quality strategic tools (Manoharan, Muralidharan & Deshmukh, 2009). Outcomes, achievements, and successes are all manifestations of performance (Rothwell, 2005). To Hasibuan (2009), performance is the product of hard labor based on abilities, experience, sincerity, and the amount of time spent completing a task. Employee performance describes the work that an individual or a group of employees in an organization may conduct in accordance with their individual rights and duties in order to achieve organizational goals (Ariussanto, Tarigan, Sitepu, & Singh, 2020). This suggests that individual and organizational success are inextricably intertwined, hence, if a person performs well, the organization's performance is likely to be great as well.

iii. Employee Reward Management

For every individual at the peck of taking up a job opportunity, various factors are being considered which ranges from the working condition, the organization's reputation, available opportunities for training, how secure the job, and most prominently is the job reward (Itika, 2011). According to Armstrong (2010), compensation and reward management is responsible for the planning, execution, and maintenance of the interconnected reward processes, practices, and procedures aimed at satisfying the demands of both the organization and its stakeholders in order for the organization to operate fairly, equitably, and consistently. Furthermore, Bob (2011) emphasized that compensation and reward administration entails identifying job values, designing and sustaining pay structures, rewarding for performance, competence, and skill, and

providing benefits to employees. This is more than just the concerns for money; it entails non-monetary mechanisms that generate intrinsic or extrinsic desire. It is vital to highlight that compensation and reward management encompasses non-monetary rewards like as recognition, learning and development opportunities, and increased work responsibility in addition to salary and benefits.

iv. Employee Relations

The most important resources and valuable assets in an organization have been established to be employees, and the extent to which they perform their work directly impacts the success of an organization (Sequeira & Dhriti, 2015). Thus, maintaining a healthy relationship becomes a prerequisite for any organization to be successful. This is because when a relationship between employers and employees within the organization is not well nurtured to avoid conflicting cases, its result in unproductive behavior. Itika (2011) expressed that employee relations is the new veil of industrial relation, as it was believed there is more to which industrial relations can cover within an organization than interaction between the workforce and their trade unions, employers and their organizations, the state via different laws and labor legislation, as well as processes and the availability of remedies where specific parties are harmed.

Organizational Effectiveness

Despite the difficulty in defining organizational effectiveness, various studies such as (Zheng, Yang & McLean, 2010; Aydin & Ceylan, 2009; Cummings & Worley, 2004) described organization effectiveness as “the extent to which the organization is able to achieve its goals through the systematic application of acquired knowledge and resources”. It is the concept of how effective an organization is in obtaining the outcomes it seeks, and it symbolizes how regular they are with their approach and procedures in order to achieve the company's long-term goal. The term "organizational effectiveness" is commonly used to refer to goal achievement. It is a functional idea rather than a structural concept in this sense. Furthermore, it is likely to be most valuable in comparative organizational research, that is, in relational rather than absolute terms, although the notion might also be employed developmentally to evaluate the efficacy of the same organization through time. In the study of industrial organizations, effectiveness has traditionally been regarded and operationalized primarily in terms of production.

Effectiveness is a reflection of an organization's internal dynamic operations and values (Oghojafor, Muo & Aduloju, 2012). Akpan and Nsien (2017) developed the perspective of Scriven, (2007) to explain organizational effectiveness as “the degree to which the social system of an organization, given available resources, are able to accomplish its objectives without incapacitating their resources and without placing undue stress upon its members. This simply means that effectiveness in an organization encompasses of organizational productivity, organizational flexibility which enable them to adjust and adapt to changes, and finally absence of conflict, tension or strains between groups or individuals within the organization.

Theoretical Review

The relationship between HR practices and organizational effectiveness can be viewed from the perspectives of the resource based view theory, which this study is anchored on. The resource based view theory indicates that despite the existence of various resources within the organization, it is the human resources that possess a unique character among all other resources that creates a competitive advantage for the organization (Delery & Roumpi (2017).

The resource based view theory indicates that despite the existence of various resources within the organization, it is the human resources that possess a unique character among all other resources that creates a competitive advantage for the organization (Delery & Roumpi (2017). The human resource are the ones who exploits all other available resources needed to achieve an organization's goal. To ensure that the human resources meets all these criteria, the human resource unit of the organization has an important role to play (Armstrong (2012). These roles are mostly reflected through the practices that are being put in place as Wright, McMahan, and McWilliams (1994) noted that the interaction between the human capital pool and the human resource management practice is the only way through which the competitive advantage of an organization can be sustained.

The resource-based perspective has had a significant impact on human resource management thought. It gives justification for prioritizing resourcing operations, particularly those involving talent management. It can also be utilized to increase the importance of human resource in achieving strategic objectives (Armstrong, 2012). People in the organization become the focus of the resource-based view, their contributions are monitored and made more apparent, the way people are managed can be seen to add value, and money spent on people may be regarded as an investment rather than a cost.

Empirical Review

Manoharan, Muralidharan & Deshmukh (2009) conducted a study on performance appraisal as one of the HR practices using data envelopment analysis (DEA), most especially in making decisions. The study posited DEA as an effective best practice in appraising the performance of an employee within the organization, as this will improve employee's performance and overall effectiveness of the organization better unlike the traditional methods of appraising performance. Thus, rating the performance of employees requires the use of models that are computer-based to replace the traditional ways through which performance are being rated. Also, it was recommended that based on the DEA result, the performance of employees can be improved when the organization give room for training, enhancement of talents and adding to qualification when a need arises.

Absar, Nimalathan & Jilani (2010) studied the impact human resource management practices among manufacturing firms in Bangladesh has on the performance of their organizations. Fifty manufacturing firms participated in the study, and the result revealed a significant association, while only one HR practice (performance appraisal has a significant impact, while the other practices (recruitment and selection, training and development as well as compensation) do not. Contrary to this result, training and development in the study of Olaniyan & Ojo (2008)

were recommended as crucial HR practices which help the organization to enhance its effectiveness. This assertion was made based on an empirical review.

However, when compared with the study of Tan and Nasurdin (2011) on the direct relationships that exists between the practice of HRM and innovation of 171 sampled large manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Performance appraisal and training were found to significantly affect innovation within an organization, although there exists a positive effect of training on three dimensions of organization innovation, while performance appraisal only positively affects one of the innovation dimensions.

Extending the notion of HR practices, a study by Quansah (2013) evaluated the employees' perception of HR practices among rural banks. Four (4) branches of rural banks were surveyed, where 150 employees within the managerial and non-managerial levels were sampled using purposive and convenience sampling techniques. The findings from the study reflected a poor perception of the employees on the HR practices within their organization. The study pointed out that HR practices formulated and implemented are improperly done and most times handled by non-HR experts. Thus, it was recommended that most banks in rural areas require much dedication to creating HR units filled with experts, as this will enhance the effectiveness of the organization.

Also, performance appraisal, training and information technology were focused on by Abang, May-Chiun and Maw (2015) as HR practices that affect the effectiveness of manufacturing firms using incentives as a moderator. 85 Manufacturing firms in Malaysia who volunteered to participate in the survey were sampled. The finding of the study revealed that the performance of the organization was directly impacted by only training and information technology, while incentive which was positively related to the performance of an organization had no significant moderation effect on HR practices and organizational performance.

Similarly, empowerment was captured as an HR practice, and how it affects the performance of an organization, while mediated by performance appraisal in a study by Rajalingam, Junaimah & Abdul Ghani (2015). Primary data were sourced by surveying 200 employees from manufacturing firms in Malaysia through the use of a questionnaire. The responses were analyzed using SPSS, and the result established that the performance of an organization is not influenced by some empowerment tools such as power, knowledge, sharing information and reward. Also, there was no significant mediation through performance appraisal.

Furthermore, Al-Hawari & Shdefat (2016) in their study also aimed to analyze the impact of HR practices on the satisfaction of employees with their job. The specific practices concentrate on are "HR planning, selection and appointment, rewards and motivation, training programs, and performance evaluation". The study concentrated on the employee of Al-Rajhi cement factory in Jordan, from which 241 valid responses were retrieved from the 300 copies of the questionnaire that was administered to them. The result indicated that only HR planning, selection and appointment and training programs significantly affect the satisfaction of employees with their job.

Mehmood, Awais, Afzal, Shahzadi & Khalid (2017) also targeted 90 employees in both public and private universities who responded to a 49 item questionnaire in order to ascertain the impact HR practice have on the performance of an organization. It was established from the study that the performance of an organization can be achieved when the commitment of the employee are increased. They further recommended that to enhance employees commitment, there is a need to improve the level of their satisfaction through appropriately compensating their employees for the work done, while also ensuring that the policies and working conditions are favorable to the employees.

In addition, Sani and Worlu (2018) conducted a study on the connection between “HRMP and managerial performance of manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt”. Primary data was sourced using a structured questionnaire and was analyzed using Spearman’s Rank Order Correlation Coefficient through SPSS. Job security and extensive on-the-job training were revealed to best improve the performance of employees in managerial positions.

3.0 Material and Methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is quantitative in nature, and based on the hypothetical deductive approach. This study was carried out among two listed food manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This sub-sector was selected because food contribute about 11.5%, to Nigeria GDP, which is a higher percentage than every other sub-sector in the manufacturing sector (NBS cited in Trade Economics 2021). Thus, food products remain the largest sub-sector in the Nigerian manufacturing industry (Nwulu, 2018). In addition, over 88% of Nigeria’s top food firms have their headquarters and plant locations within the southwest geopolitical zone, with more concentration in Lagos and Ogun states (Asoko Insight, 2019). Thus, the geographical scope of the study was Lagos and Ogun state, which are two states out of the six states in Southwest Nigeria. These states were selected because the food manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria that are listed in the Nigeria Stock Exchange (Now Nigeria Exchange Group) as at 2021 are situated there. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting one food manufacturing firm from each state (Lagos and Ogun state). Primary data was sourced from the selected firms through the use of a well-structured closed ended questionnaire as a research instrument. This instrument was used to elicit first-hand information from the respondents, who are employees of the selected food manufacturing firms. The study target population was 1478 employees, and using the survey monkey sample size calculator, 373 employees were sampled. Copies of the questionnaire were administered through the Human resource Department of the selected firms. In addition, an online survey was used to administer the research instrument through the use of google form. This was to help access employees who were physically not accessible due to the remote work policy in place within the organization during the data collection process.

The human resource management practices captured in this study are employees’ learning and development, employees’ performance appraisal, employees’ reward management, and employees’ relations. A Cronbach alpha test was conducted to ensure the reliability of the instruments used to measure the variable, the result revealed a value \geq than 0.70 on each of

the constructs in the study. PLS-SEM was the data analysis technique used in deriving the findings for the study. The statistical package used was SmartPLS.

4.0 Results and Discussion

Effect of Selected HR Practices on Organizational Effectiveness

The model in Figure 1 reveals the path coefficient and bootstrapping of all constructs using the PLS-SEM analysis in assessing the effect of selected HR practices on organizational effectiveness. Learning and Development (LD), Performance Appraisal (PA), Reward Management (RM) and Employee Relations (ER) were the four HR practices selected. The path coefficient explains the degree (-1 and +1) to which the independent constructs (LD, PA, RM, ER) influences the dependent construct (OE). A strong positive effect occurs when the coefficients are closer to +1, while a strong negative effect occurs when the coefficients are closer to -1.

The model result in Figure 1 indicated that between: LD and OE ($\beta=.144$, $T_{val} = 0.943$, $F_{val} = 0.023$), PA and OE ($\beta= -0.101$, $T_{val} = 0.597$, $F_{val} = 0.012$); RM and OE ($\beta=.532$, $T_{val} = 6.343$, $F_{val} = 0.400$); ER and OE ($\beta=.371$, $T_{val} = 5.000$, $F_{val} = 0.202$). This indicates that learning and development have a positive weak effect on organizational effectiveness, performance appraisal have a negative weak effect on organizational effectiveness, reward management has a positive strong effect on organizational effectiveness, while employee relations have a positive strong effect on organizational effectiveness. Thus, only two HR practices (RM and ER) out of the four practices have a positive effect on the psychological wellbeing of the employee. However, reward management has the highest size of effect on the psychological well-being of employees. In addition, the R square statistic value of 0.641 in figure 4.5 however depicts that the selected HR practices jointly account for about 64.1% contribution to the effectiveness of an organization.

Figure 1: PLS Algorithm for Human resource management Practices and Organizational Effectiveness

Source: Field Survey, 2021 (SmartPLS Output)

v. Test of Hypothesis

H0₁: The selected HR practices do not have a significant effect on the effectiveness of food manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria

The p-values for the path coefficients indicate the significance of the hypothesis, using a 5000 bootstrapping, at 95% level of confidence (0.05). Each practice was used to form a sub hypothesis, and the result in Table 1 established that Learning and development (Hypothesis 1a) does not significantly predict organizational effectiveness ($\beta=0.144$, $p=0.346$), therefore refusing to reject the null hypothesis. Performance appraisal (Hypothesis 1b) also does not significantly predict organizational effectiveness ($\beta= -0.101$, $p=0.563$), therefore refusing to reject the null hypothesis. However, reward management (Hypothesis 1c) significantly predict organizational effectiveness ($\beta=0.532$, $p=0.000$), therefore rejecting the null hypothesis. Finally, employee relations (Hypothesis 1d) have a significant prediction on organizational effectiveness ($\beta=0.371$, $p=0.000$), therefore rejecting the null hypothesis.

Thus, from hypothesis, only two of the sub hypotheses (RW, ER) was significant, while the other two (LD, PA) are not significant HR practices that underscores the effectiveness of an organization.

Table 1: Summary of Hypotheses Model Results

Structural estimates (Hypotheses testing)					Decision on Null Hypothesis
Path	β	T-Value	f^2	p value	
ER → OE	0.371	5.000*	0.202	0.000	Rejected
LD → OE	0.144	0.943	0.023	0.346	Not Rejected
PA → OE	-0.101	0.579	0.012	0.563	Not Rejected
RM → OE	0.532	6.343*	0.400	0.000	Rejected

Note: *= $p < 0.05$, Significance (2-tailed)

Source: Field Survey, 2021 (SmartPLS Output)

Discussion

Findings of the study revealed that the human resource management practices had 64.1% contribution to the effectiveness of food manufacturing firms in Nigeria (see fig 1). Reward management and employee relation were the only positively significant human resource management practice that affects the effectiveness of the food manufacturing firms, however, reward management had a stronger positive effect than employee relations. On the other side, learning and development and performance appraisal do not significantly affect the effectiveness of the food manufacturing firms. Although learning and development had a weak positive effect which was not significant to the effectiveness of the organizations, the performance appraisal effect remains negatively insignificant. This finding is partially in line with the study of Rana and Malik (2017) as well as Teimouri, Hosseini, Imani and Bagheri (2018) where HR practices significantly affect the effectiveness of an organization. In their case, training and performance appraisal were significant HR practices to the effectiveness of an organization, while in this current study, their effect on organizational effectiveness was not significant. The difference in findings may be as a result of a difference in how the practices are implemented within the organizations that were concentrated on.

5.0 Conclusion

The connection between HR practices and effectiveness is still significant in every organization as long as the human effort is required, and the complexity that emanates from humans cannot be overlooked when it comes to managing human resources. Achieving effectiveness in an organization requires the existence of positive relationship within the organization, either between management and employee or among the employees themselves. In addition, the extent to which the employees are satisfied with the organizational reward packages (both financial and non-financial) becomes important. Thus, the study concludes that to enhance the effectiveness of an organization, both financial and non-financial reward should be combined in rewarding employees within the organizations. Also employee relation practices such as protecting employees' interests and fostering a direct employer-employee relationship should be embraced within organizations, as these are the best practice through which the effectiveness of an organization can be achieved.

Although, developing the employees and appraising their performance matters a lot, the approaches adopted toward these practices are not effective enough. Thus, there is a need for proper review of the learning and development as well as the performance appraisal practices within the organizations, considering its insignificant effect on the organization's effectiveness.

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DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The author of this paper hereby declares that there are no impediments to the publication of this work.

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